

GenRes Bridge

GenRes Bridge - Joining forces for genetic resources and biodiversity management

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D4.4/D19 Strategy and priorities for delivering information services to end users

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Executive summary

The deliverable D19/D4.4 of the GenRes Bridge project presents the overarching strategy on the documentation on Genetic Resource that has been developed to complement the overarching European Strategy on Genetic Resources (D2.4) and the new specific strategies of the three European networks of conservation of genetic resources, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN. A brief overview of the current global context concerning data on biodiversity, the achievements and current gaps of the three networks' documentation activities is provided. This is completed by an overview of some important aspects of the legal frame of constraints and opportunities arising from the current ecosystem of initiatives supporting open science. The strategy proposes to leverage and adapt to the field of documentation on genetic resources the resources developed by the scientific community to support good data management practices compliant to the FAIR principles and ensure the development of a Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable wealth of data on genetic resources. The first set of proposed activities that should be developed at an overarching level by the networks where relevant are: development of standards, technology watch, training, capacity building and awareness raising on the importance of adopting and supporting good data management practices. Ultimately, they aim at increasing the quantity and the quality of data in the central repositories of the networks and at getting these repositories internationally recognized as trusted and FAIR compliant repositories. Another set of activities will allow the three networks to increase their participation in international initiatives developing the guidelines and resources supporting open linked data in relation with research and innovation in the areas of biodiversity, agriculture and forestry.

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1. Data on genetic resources in the context of the great challenges faced by biodiversity for food, agriculture and forestry – vision and objectives

1.1. General Context

Biodiversity for food and agriculture is well recognized as indispensable for sustainable and adaptable agriculture and forestry production systems as well as for healthy, sustainable and secure food systems beneficial to human health^{1,2} (Pilling *et al.* 2020a; Savary 2020; Lachat *et al.* 2018). In their latest State of the World Report³ FAO defines biodiversity for food and agriculture as *“the subset of biodiversity that contributes in one way or another to agriculture and food production. It includes the domesticated plants and animals raised in crop, livestock, forest and aquaculture systems, harvested forest and aquatic species, the wild relatives of domesticated species, other wild species harvested for food and other products, and what is known as ‘associated biodiversity’, the vast range of organisms that live in and around food and agricultural production systems, sustaining them and contributing to their output”*.

Despite its crucial importance for mankind and the existence of global plans to better conserve and manage it, biodiversity in agriculture and forestry is continuously declining^{4,5} (Pilling *et al.* 2020a, b) and the current food systems are major drivers of this decline⁶. A shift of agriculture and forestry towards agroecological production systems, where biodiversity holds a central position, is therefore promoted by the EU^{1,2,7} and globally (e.g.⁸).

As pointed out by the EC, FAO and IPBES, the development of more integrated approaches to monitor the impacts of food and forestry systems need to encompass all relevant biodiversity elements: genetic diversity in plants, animals, forests, microbes and invertebrates. However, the current lack of comprehensive data to map and monitor biodiversity for food and agriculture is among the problems that need to be overcome to better address the issue of biodiversity loss⁵ (Conde *et al.* 2019, Pilling *et al.* 2020b). FAO declared its willingness to support its members in providing data regarding their biodiversity targets and assessment needs but does not give access to the consolidated datasets in return. In addition, many publications stress the lack of comprehensive documentation about the wild segment of biodiversity, which includes wild relatives of crops or livestock, particularly fisheries, and, to a lesser extent given some targeted global effort under the auspices of FAO, forest trees (e.g.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_fr

² https://ec.europa.eu/food/farm2fork_en

³ <http://www.fao.org/state-of-biodiversity-for-food-agriculture/en/>; <http://aims.fao.org/news/state-world%E2%80%99s-biodiversity-food-and-agriculture-fao-2019-based-data>

⁴ <https://ipbes.net/global-assessment>

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/eca/special-reports/biodiversity-13-2020/en/>

⁶ http://teebweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Foundations_Report_Final_October.pdf

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁸ <http://www.fao.org/agroecology/overview/en/>

Seibold *et al.* 2019; Conde *et al.* 2019; Pilling *et al.* 2020b). In relation to cultivated or domesticated genetic resources (GR), there is also a lack of data on the threat status of animal breeds and of a global method to assess the current use of crop varieties by farmers (Pilling *et al.* 2020b).

To summarize, collecting, finding and accessing updated and comprehensive data on existing biodiversity is still a challenge, whatever the category of biodiversity considered within FAO's definition. In its last report⁹, IPBES lists in detail gaps, which impede the integration of data on adaptive and production traits, usage and conservation, ecosystem services, etc. Yet, addressing these gaps is imperative as such knowledge is driving management strategies as well as the use of GR for addressing the major global challenges currently faced by humanity (climate change, biodiversity loss, global health), which in turn might also contribute to their sustainable conservation¹⁰.

GR, as those managed by the three network partners of the GenRes Bridge project, play an important role in the food, agriculture and forestry biodiversity and need to be conserved, sustainably used, and made accessible. The various outputs of the GenRes Bridge project have illuminated many areas for improvement, such as the necessity to better combine *in situ* and *ex situ* approaches for GR conservation and to improve GR monitoring, to diversify the use of GR and to intensify GR characterization¹⁰. In most of these activities, management and access to information plays a central role with three important questions :

- 1) What technical infrastructure and associated governance are needed (and feasible) for proper collection, curation and sharing of information on GR?
- 2) How do this infrastructure and its governance develop mechanisms to address the ethical and legal aspects of data property in relation with data producers and users' expectations and with data access?
- 3) How should different types of information on GR be combined to provide a true image of their conservation state, characteristics and use, taking into account the different priorities of the three European networks ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN in terms of data integration?

Some elements to address these questions have already been provided by the three European networks for the conservation of GR in the plant, animal and forestry domains as presented for the current state of art in section 1.3 of this document and for the future in their newly developed domain specific strategies¹¹, which complement the European Strategy on GR. The three domains deal with their own stakeholder communities and use practices, their own types of biological material and methodologies for conserving and making them available to users. The aim of the present document is to propose an overarching strategy to create synergisms between the three domains in support of their specific objectives on data management and access. Indeed, certain resources, such as training or capacity building on the FAIR principles or even proper ontology or identifier management, are relevant to all domains. Developing these supporting resources for documentation activities independently would not only generate unnecessary costs, it would also create incompatibility between them,

⁹ <https://ipbes.net/global-assessment>

¹⁰ see GenRes Bridge deliverable D2.4 – A European Genetic Resource Strategy, for more details

¹¹ the new strategies of the three networks for the conservation of GR, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN should be released by the end of 2021.

complicating exchanges of information and impeding data integration across domains, when needed.

The strategy developed here addresses data and associated metadata on the GR conserved by the three European networks for GR: passport data of breeds, units of conservation and accessions; characterization data of individuals or populations, metadata on the structures in charge of the conservation and their practices. It focusses on infrastructural elements and skills needed to ensure proper standardised data collection and management, allowing efficient data sharing. These activities concern the data providers such as collection curators and scientists. It suggests tools, standards and capacity building (training, networking activities supporting skill development) required for their successful implementation. Although documentation activities and associated priorities will generally be domain specific, the need to properly document certain types of data is generic, as are some supporting tools and activities.

The strategy also aims to enable the development of cross-disciplinary or (when appropriate) cross-domain data integrations that support decision-making for (i) the European networks for GR and policy makers for monitoring their strategies on GR and (ii) scientists, breeders and extension services for research and development purposes. The development of supporting knowledge to such activities can involve inclusion of third party information, such as ecological or climatological geolocalized data. Such development of cross domain applications will result in overviews that allow better informed decision-making from a low integration level of e.g. the composition of collections at sites under changing climatological conditions, to a high integration level such as the one developed in GenRes Bridge demonstration cases¹². Enabling data interoperability with relevant information systems will allow the delivery of useful information to a diverse panel of end users and contribute to a knowledge base for GR conservation and sustainable use.

In all cases involving data services, proper information management is the key. Data management encompasses underlying numeric infrastructures, frameworks for capacity and skills building including engaging new research fields. It also requires addressing user's expectations as well as legal and ethical issues about data sharing (OECD 2020) including in the context of public/private partnerships. The governance of data on GR must take into account national and global policies specific to data, align technically with linked global data initiatives on biodiversity and leverage existing resources developed to support FAIR¹³ compliant data management.

To finish setting the scene and provide context around the management of data on GR, a brief summary of current policies and international initiatives about data on biodiversity and food is presented in section 1.2. The current state of activities on documentation of the three European networks, ECPGR, ERFP, EUFORGEN is then described in section 1.3 and an overview of the main users of their documentation activities in 1.4.

¹² Deliverable D3.2 – GenRes Bridge demonstration cases : <http://www.genresbridge.eu/about-us/news/news/case-studies-point-to-integrated-conservation-of-genetic-resources/>

¹³ See Figure 1 and section 1.2.2 for more details on the FAIR principles aiming at making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

1.2. Policies and international initiatives about data on biodiversity for food, agriculture and forestry

With the numeric revolution undergone by our societies, data has become a major resource and preoccupation of citizens, organizations and industry. Two different movements are relevant for consideration here :

- National and international regulations and policies dealing with ethical issues related to data and data ownership
- International endeavours towards “machine readable” data that led to the development of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson *et al.* 2016) and a growing number of initiatives aiming at implementing these principles at different scales and in different communities of interest.

In the next two sections some of these policies and initiatives relevant to all domains are briefly described to set up the general context of documentation activities and the opportunities that can be leveraged to improve their efficiency.

1.2.1. Ethical and data ownership related policies

General Data Protection Regulation

The recent implementation in the EU of the General Data Protection Regulation¹⁴ has an impact regarding the reporting scale of data on GR. Even when direct personal information is not provided, a very precise location of a farm, a field or a forest may automatically allow the identification of the owner. To avoid this risk of infringing on privacy, the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics¹⁵ has been set up at the European level, which should be used to geolocalize GR used in agriculture.

The Nagoya Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol on Access to GR and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization¹⁶ is an international agreement in the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)¹⁷, which aims at sharing the benefits arising from the utilization of GR in a fair and equitable way and entered into force on 12 October 2014. The main target of the protocol is the GR itself, as a physical object. However, in relation with data, the protocol also addresses traditional knowledge from indigenous and local communities associated with GR. Contracting Parties are to take measures to ensure these communities’ prior informed consent, and fair and equitable benefit-sharing, keeping in mind community laws and procedures as well as customary use and exchange¹⁸.

More recently, negotiations regarding ‘digital sequence information (DSI)’ in the context of access and benefit sharing (ABS) of GR have been started and are still ongoing in the frame of the CBD¹⁹. The concern expressed by a number of Countries in the global South arose from

¹⁴ GDPR, https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

¹⁵ NUTS, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background>

¹⁶ <https://www.cbd.int/abs/>

¹⁷ <https://www.cbd.int/>

¹⁸ <https://www.cbd.int/traditional/Protocol.shtml>

¹⁹ See the dedicated pages of the CBD on the subject, <https://www.cbd.int/dsi-gr/>, and in particular a video to explain the issue to a large public : <https://youtu.be/xJ0ZjpY0VQo>

the fact that using the appropriate genetic information in combination with advanced genome editing techniques could provide a way of avoiding the need for access to physical biological material and thus escape from ABS regulations. This could induce a loss of value for the countries where the initial resource, which was used to get the information, originated from. Access to data is something to be managed adequately in relation to private stakeholders using the GR (e.g. in public private partnerships). These stakeholders thus wish to extend the data and knowledge requiring prior consent before exchange to DSI, a notion whose scope is still to be better defined.

A regulation for access to sequence data associated with GR would impair machine-actionable data access and re-use but also probably create additional social barriers towards open science practices. It would also be in contradiction with the open data access models of the international sequence archives (Genbank²⁰, European Nucleotide Archive²¹, DNA Data Bank of Japan²²) and would therefore probably also lead to an increase of data scattering with a necessity to locally fund long term data management and regulated access. (see e.g.^{23,24}). The European Union is currently developing a position on the subject.

INSPIRE

The European INSPIRE open data policy supports international observatories on environment strategies and citizen rights to be informed on environmental issues. This has led to the INSPIRE regulation²⁵ that enforces an automatic declaration of data related to activities, which may impact the environment. It is associated with the INSPIRE infrastructure²⁶ that supports the compliance with the regulation through a series of services such as a common standard, the Ecology Metadata Language (EML), registry services that allow assigning unique identifiers to data sets or key elements within datasets, trainings, etc. Yet this language is not well adapted to the monitoring of genetic diversity.

1.2.2. International endeavours towards machine readable data related to biodiversity

In the research domain, sharing knowledge and data has always been important, leading to the development of both dedicated resources and policies. The numeric revolution of knowledge and data sharing started in the 80's with the development of important global resources such as the INSDC sequence archives²⁷, the GBIF facility²⁸, full text archives of life science journals and literature (e.g.²⁹) as well as a series of recommendations by the scientific

²⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

²¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

²² <https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/>

²³ <https://iccwbo.org/content/uploads/sites/3/2018/06/7-joint-stakeholder-statement-on-digital-sequence-information-01-08-201.pdf>; <https://www.cbd.int/abs/DSI-views/CETAF-DSI.pdf>

²⁴ <https://iccwbo.org/content/uploads/sites/3/2018/06/7-joint-stakeholder-statement-on-digital-sequence-information-01-08-201.pdf>

²⁵ INSPIRE Directive 2007/2/EC: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/2019-06-26>

²⁶ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>

²⁷ International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, www.insdc.org

²⁸ www.gbif.org

²⁹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov> › pmc

societies on standards and deposition archives associated with enforcements by scientific journals to follow these recommendations for publishing. More recently, the release of a framework of policies, incentive measures, international initiatives, infrastructures and resources aimed at better democratizing Open Science practices at the level of each scientist.

Open Science

The guidelines supporting data openness have been developed by the Force11 consortium³⁰ as the FAIR principles that list the important practices to ultimately make data fully machine-actionable with four angles of view: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (Wilkinson *et al.* 2016; Figure 1). Access and reuse are conditioned by technical recommendations to be followed but also by the policy on data ownership that should be detailed using the Creative Commons Attribution framework under the FAIR recommendations. Open science policy may encounter some limits when research is implemented in partnership with private partners who may have confidentiality requirements and need to protect their commercial strategy. This can be the case in partnerships with companies, but also in the case of participatory science, where individual farmers may want their know-how to be properly recognized when re-used. In these cases, a contractual basis is needed to plan the release of data and some new public-private operators are developing data market places to meet this challenge (e.g. ^{31, 32}).

Figure 1 : The FAIR principles refer to three types of entities: data, metadata (information about the data), and the infrastructure to manage, access and re-use the data. For instance, principle F4 defines that both metadata and data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource (the infrastructure component). Adapted from Wilkinson *et al.* 2013 and³³.

³⁰ <https://www.force11.org/>

³¹ www.agdatahub.eu

³² www.agrimetrics.co.uk

³³ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

The European commission (EC) is actively developing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)³⁴ to support its open science policy. This is done through a series of incentives such as enforcing the development of data-management plans for all projects under EC research programs or opening calls to fund the contribution of EU research infrastructures to develop the EOSC. A set of joint actions have also been funded by the EU to facilitate interoperability of data within clusters of research infrastructures, including a cluster for environmental sciences (ENVRI-FAIR³⁵) and a cluster for life sciences (EOSC-Life³⁶). From 2020, EOSC will be implemented as a co-programmed partnership under Horizon Europe, with the set up of an EOSC association to manage its stakeholders.

At the global level, the implementation of the open science policy is supported by many initiatives such as: (i) the inter-governmental science driven Research Data Alliance³⁷ that has been very successful in developing an environment where experts of all countries can agree on common standards and address new issues or (ii) the Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition network (GODAN)³⁸ supported by public and private international donors, which has built a map of existing standards for agriculture and food³⁹, including the Vocabularies, Metadata Sets and Tools (VEST) Directory of FAO and its portal of guidelines⁴⁰.

Research infrastructures

Research infrastructures have also been instrumental in the development of resources supporting open data for research. In the context of GR, several examples can be of interest and some are currently involved together into a working group aiming at improving the interoperability of their data⁴¹.

- GBIF, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility⁴², is an international network and research infrastructure funded by governments and aims at providing open access to data on all biodiversity to anyone, anywhere. GBIF works through a network of participating countries and organisations. It provides data-holding institutions around the world with common standards (E.g Darwin Core) and open-source tools that enable them to share information about where and when species have been recorded. GBIF currently includes over 1,7 billion biodiversity occurrence records. In addition, many publishers provide open access to their datasets using machine-readable Creative Commons licence designations, allowing scientists, researchers and others to apply the data in a range of analyses and studies.
- DiSSCo, Distributed System of Scientific Collections, is a European infrastructure for natural science collections⁴³. The DiSSCo gathers natural history museums, botanic gardens and collection-holding universities with the aim to get European natural

³⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-cloud>

³⁵ <https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/>

³⁶ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

³⁷ www.rda.org

³⁸ <https://www.godan.info/>

³⁹ Pesce V, Tennison J, Mey L *et al.* A Map of Agri-food Data Standards [version 1; not peer reviewed].

F1000Research 2018, 7:177 (document) (<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1115260.1>)

⁴⁰ <http://aims.fao.org/fr/vest-registry/metadata-sets> and <https://vest.agrisemantics.org/>

⁴¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/biodiversity>

⁴² <https://www.gbif.org/>

⁴³ <https://www.dissco.eu/>

science assets under common curation, access, policies and practices, and to ensure that the data complies with FAIR principles.

- ELIXIR, the European distributed Infrastructure of Bioinformatics for the life sciences⁴⁴, coordinates, integrates and sustains bioinformatics resources across its member states and enables users in academia and industry to access numeric services that are vital for their research. The institutes developing and maintaining major international archives for omics data (e.g. European Nucleotide Archive, Swiss Prot) are members of ELIXIR (e.g. EMBL-EBI, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics).
- LifeWatch⁴⁵ is a European Infrastructure Consortium providing modeling facilities to support research on biodiversity organization and ecosystem functions and services.

Other global initiatives, such as The Global Genome Biodiversity Network⁴⁶ or, focussed on plants, DivSeek Intl⁴⁷, complete the landscape of networks enabling global development, dissemination and capacity building on documentation on GR.

GEO-Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO-BON)

Beyond Europe, initiatives have led to the setting up of international networks collecting data on biodiversity, such as the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), which is an intergovernmental partnership connecting government institutions, academic and research institutions, data providers, businesses, engineers, scientists and experts with a mandate on earth observation. GEO aims at coordinating and sustaining access to open data for researchers and policy makers and for decision making for a sustainable planet. GEO has established several observation networks, one of it being the GEO-Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO-BON), which has defined a set of Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs; Pereira *et al.* 2013), aimed at providing a common list of indicators of biodiversity at different scales. Being based on the population genetics theory, the EBVs related to within-species or between-species genetic diversity, either wild or domestic, have been well defined and can find a consensus, whereas EBVs at the level of ecosystem structure or function are much more difficult to define. Collecting data to calculate EBVs requires a dedicated budget and an appropriate information system. Thus, the implementation of an information system for GR in Europe should be supported, with the aim to provide European data on EBVs for genetic diversity that would be comparable across continents. The GEO-BON also encourages setting up national 'BON's, which would facilitate the process.

⁴⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.lifewatch.eu/>

⁴⁶ GGBN: <https://www.ggbn.org/>

⁴⁷ DivSeek International Network Inc : <https://divseekintl.org/>

1.3. Current activities related to documentation in the three European networks, ERFP, EUFORGEN and ECPGR— achievements and limitations

The current activities of the three European networks, ERFP, EUFORGEN and ECPGR are presented in the following paragraphs. Their priorities in terms of documentation linked to their main stakeholders, their achievements and limitations are described below together with a brief assessment of the FAIRness of their central repositories. This review and analysis of the current context was completed by a SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity and Threat) developed by the GenResBridge partners (see Annex 1).

1.3.1. Documentation of Domestic Animal Genetic Resources in the frame of the ERFP

At country level, the demographic status of farm animal breeds is monitored by National Coordinators and relevant information is gathered through characterization, surveying and monitoring activities by breeders associations and other actors. Different information systems exist in countries including databases of herd books and other specific domestic animal GR related databases. The Domestic Animal Diversity Information System (DAD-IS⁴⁸) is the global information system for domestic animal GR developed and maintained by FAO. The European Farm Animal Biodiversity Information System (EFABIS⁴⁹) is the source of European breed-related data for the DAD-IS. EFABIS serves as the platform for the exchange of national data on domestic animal GR, provided by the European National Coordinators and is managed by the ERFP and FAO. It contains data on breed characteristics, population size and risk status as well as breed related GR collections. Countries are able to set up their own national information systems within EFABIS (national node) and at present, five countries operate such national nodes. The other European countries implement their data directly from national information systems to EFABIS or DAD-IS. Within ERFP, the working group Documentation and Information is responsible for promoting regular updates of national data, for enhancing the quality of the data in EFABIS, and for initiating further development of EFABIS. Breed related data in EFABIS should include both population census data (*in situ*) and summary data on the amount of material stored in gene banks (*ex situ*). DAD-IS is providing indicators based on these data, in particular SDG 2.5.1 and 2.5.2 indicators, but the status and trend reports of FAO include additional monitoring data⁵⁰. Moreover, both phenotypic and genomic data, at the level of breeds, breeding animals and gene bank samples, are relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of domestic animal GR. The EUGENA network of gene banks (governed by ERFP) provides public access to (meta)data of gene bank collections at European level, and recently the Horizon 2020 IMAGE project has developed a European data infrastructure for gene bank collections in collaboration with EBI, which also facilitates access to gene bank samples or breed related genomic data in EBI databases⁵¹.

⁴⁸ <http://www.fao.org/dad-is/en/>

⁴⁹ <http://www.fao.org/dad-is/regional-national-nodes/efabis/en/>

⁵⁰ See GenRes Bridge milestone MS3.6 -Indicators for efficiency and effectiveness of the conservation and management of GenRes

⁵¹ <https://www.image2020genebank.eu/?idm=36&lang=en>

1.3.2. Documentation of Forest Genetic Resources in the frame of EUFORGEN

EUFORGEN develops and maintains the European Information System on Forest GR (EUFGIS⁵²), a unique system which supports countries in identifying gaps in conservation of forest species as well as in setting priorities to fill these conservation gaps. The system is a reference for countries and can be used as a national information system. Importantly, it enables high-quality reporting for international commitments, e.g. Forest Europe monitoring (indicator 4.6)⁵³. The EUFORGEN National Coordinators (or relevant authority in case of non-member countries) nominate National Focal Points who are responsible for collecting and maintaining information on forest GR as part of national forest GR inventories or any similar arrangement a country may have in place for obtaining and maintaining the data. The EUFGIS National Focal Points are expected to update national data sets in the information system, participate in EUFGIS-related meetings and training and provide inputs to further development of the EUFGIS information system and new initiatives on forest GR documentation, as needed.

1.3.3. Documentation of Plant Genetic Resources in the frame of ECPGR

Objective 2 of ECPGR for Phase X (2019-2023) is to provide passport and phenotypic information of actively conserved European Plant GR for Food and Agriculture (PGRFA) conserved *ex situ* through the European Search Catalogue for Plant GR, EURISCO⁵⁴. EURISCO was initially created through the EU-funded project EPGRIS and has been available online since 2003. It enables to centrally collect passport data of *ex situ* accessions from all National Inventories in Europe, through a network of 43 National Inventory Focal Points and an agreement on the use of a standard data exchange format, based on the FAO/IPGRI Multi Crop Passport Descriptors (MCPD)⁵⁵. EURISCO forms the European hub of Genesys⁵⁶, the platform maintained by the Crop Trust for information on worldwide PGRFA conserved in Gene banks. More recently, EURISCO was further developed to enable hosting of non-standardized phenotypic data related to the EURISCO accessions, currently providing over 90 000 accessions with such data. Collaboration towards better harmonization of phenotypic data aligned with recent international efforts in the domain⁵⁷ is being built through the Horizon 2020 AGENT project⁵⁸.

Several crop-specific web portals and databases have been developed to guide the users to data and material (see for example the Lettuce Crop Portal⁵⁹). Such portals are now proposed

⁵² <http://www.eufgis.org/>

⁵³ See GenRes Bridge milestone MS3.6 -Indicators for efficiency and effectiveness of the conservation and management of GenRes

⁵⁴ <http://eurisco.ecpgr.org>

⁵⁵ <https://www.biodiversityinternational.org/e-library/publications/detail/faobiodiversity-multi-crop-passport-descriptors-v21-mcpd-v21/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.genesys-pgr.org/>

⁵⁷ www.miappe.org

⁵⁸ <https://agent-project.eu/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.pgrportal.nl/en/Lettuce-genetic-resources-Portal.htm>

to be supported by automatic links with EURISCO for the maintenance of updated inventories, as for instance the Poa portal⁶⁰. However, the sustainability of such portals currently relies on limited project funds and the enthusiasm of the creator-teams. There is a need to develop a generic tool box that could be used to more efficiently sustain these portals.

Inclusion of relevant data on *in situ* Crop Wild Relatives (CWR) in EURISCO is among the objectives of ECPGR in its Phase X⁶¹. The first problem to address regarding *in situ* data has been the lack of an agreement on a structured system for data upload, similar to the MCPD standard used by National Inventory Focal Points for uploading *ex situ* data. FAO has recently published a globally agreed descriptor list for CWR *in situ* conservation⁶², which will support the development of a data exchange standard format. In case of on-farm data, it has so far been difficult to reach an agreement on what type of data should be gathered and for what purpose. The Horizon 2020 project Farmer's Pride⁶³ created a proposal for the technical extension of EURISCO for gathering both *in situ* CWR and on-farm metadata, which is under discussion within the ECPGR network to further precise the scope and the underlying organization with the countries to stream the data.

The current role of EURISCO in the international PGR information landscape is important, especially its networking function, operating as a hub for the European national inventories and acting as a platform for the European PGR gene bank documentation community. A future repartition of roles between EURISCO (supporting the European PGR documentation community, linking between European PGR actors and Genesys), Genesys (as global repository of PGR accession-related data and provision of access), and the World Information and Early Warning System on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (WIEWS, providing metadata on holding organizations) is being considered. The EURISCO and Genesys interfaces are currently partially overlapping and this may require simplification in the future. The possible role of EURISCO regarding inclusion of, or linkage to, -omics data will be re-considered in the near future and will probably focus more on data provider support and data quality.

⁶⁰ <http://poa.ipk-gatersleben.de/>

⁶¹ https://www.ecpgr.cgiar.org/fileadmin/templates/ecpgr.org/upload/TORs_PHase_IX/Revised_Objectives_final_web_27_06_2028.pdf

⁶² <http://www.fao.org/3/cb0681en/cb0681en.pdf>

⁶³ <http://www.farmerspride.eu/>

1.3.4. Evaluation of the alignment to the FAIR principles of the central repositories of the three European networks, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN

An evaluation of the three main central databases of the networks against the FAIR principles was carried out in the frame of the GenRes Bridge project⁶⁴ with the objective to guide future improvements.

Two frameworks were considered for this evaluation :

- The Core Trust Seal⁶⁵: this framework does not only address the FAIRness of repositories but also their governance and sustainability, which are also extremely important elements in the long term.
- The Australian Research Data Common (ARDC) tool⁶⁶, focussed on the FAIR principles.

Both frameworks provided relevant information on the implementation of the FAIR principles in the central repositories of the three networks. Necessary improvements to meet the FAIR principles were identified for the three information systems, in particular in the domain of findability, interoperability and reusability of the data. These improvements would already enhance the data integration and re-use within each domain in addition to interoperability with data stored in external databases.

In all three cases, the governance is to be envisaged in the context of complex and heterogeneous networks (in terms of data management) providing data to the central information systems. The responsibility for data completeness and quality is shared between many stakeholders, which increases the complexity of the set up of an agreed detailed data management plan.

1.3.5. Users targeted by the information systems of the three European networks ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN

GenRes Bridge WP3 made a survey across a large panel of stakeholders about their interest in the services proposed by the three European networks, including (i) information-related services such as the domain specific databases, (ii) indicators to monitor trends and (iii) reporting on the conservation and management of GR activities⁶⁷.

The stakeholders who filled the survey gave a representative picture of the types of users of the European networks' services: among their three major activities, 56% respondents declared a research activity, 26% a Gene bank management activity, 24% were national coordinators, 22% a breeding activity and 13% a conservation activity. The other mentioned activities were split between data management, forestry, farming and international bodies. Most of the stakeholders were therefore also involved in some of the services provided by the three European networks, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN. In particular, 65% of the respondents are participating in the domain-specific databases (72% of the stakeholder having

⁶⁴ See GenRes Bridge Milestone Ms22 – Evaluation of the FAIRness of the central repositories of the three networks

⁶⁵ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/requirements/>

⁶⁶ <https://ardc.edu.au/resources/working-with-data/fair-data/fair-self-assessment-tool/>

⁶⁷ See GenRes Bridge deliverable D3.3. Report on current and potential new services for different user groups

a research activity) and 52% are participating in reporting on the conservation and management of GR but only 35% are involved in the delivery of indicators to monitor trends. These three services can, however, still be improved according to the moderate level of satisfaction of the stakeholders. Of relevance also in the context of information management, the most important services as stated by the respondents are related to the exchange of information and experiences, including best practices, guidelines, protocols and standards, databases, or training, courses and workshops. Finally, it is important to point out that the emphasis towards certain groups of stakeholders is different between the three domains: strongly balanced towards breeding activities for ECPGR, or towards conservation activities for EUFORGEN and in between for ERFP.

These differences are reflected in the current strategies of the three programmes on documentation aspects, with objectives that will tend to reduce these differences between networks in the future: e.g. EUFORGEN aims at developing characterization data on its conservation units to develop their use and ECPGR at enhancing its capacity to deliver data for monitoring the conservation of GR and its contribution to the conservation of biodiversity. Moreover, the overarching strategy for GR developed in the frame of GenRes Bridge addresses in priority the users that answered the survey⁶⁸, showing their importance for all three networks: (i) breeders, researchers and other stakeholders involved in GR conservation, characterization and management at the operational level and (ii) at the strategic level, policy markers.

Enhancing the delivery of services to these GR users requires coordination within and between the programs in the use of data standards and formats that would link to the underlying specific or, where relevant, generic Standard Operating Procedures (e.g. how to describe actual GR access; how to describe actual Conservation Unit state; how to describe an experiment associated with characterization data) and allow automatic integration of data from different databases.

1.4. Rationale for an overarching strategy supporting the delivery of information to the users of the information systems of the three European networks ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN

As described in the former sections, the existing European information management systems for plant, animal and forest GR (EURISCO, EFABIS and EUFGIS), managed respectively by the three European networks, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN, make an important contribution to documenting and monitoring the status of GR in Europe. They are central to reporting on Europe's implementation of a range of international policy commitments—including the FAO GPAs, SDGs, and Forest Europe process—and critically, provide a point of entry for users of GR. However, the value of these systems depends on the quality of data provided by the European countries.

⁶⁸ See in particular sections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 of the GenRes Bridge deliverable D2.4 – A European Genetic Resource Strategy

The key components on which the data quality and quantity depend are the national inventories for plant, domestic animal and forest GR, which provide their data to the European information management systems. It is therefore the responsibility of the European countries to develop comprehensive, up-to-date and harmonized inventories of their GR and to transfer them to the European data information systems. The quality of the data provided to the networks' central information systems ultimately relies on sufficient capacity of countries in terms of high-quality data management. Supporting coordinated efforts and capacity across countries to develop FAIR compliant data-management plans and associated technical resources for data collection and submission to appropriate international catalogs or archives is essential.

To enhance their effectiveness and impact, the European information management systems require further development to enable access to reliable genomic and phenotypic characterization data, as well as to information required to monitor conservation and threat/risk status. Interoperability of data of the European information management systems with data from other research areas within the areas of biodiversity, climate change, the bioeconomy, sociology and policy is fundamental to promote greater integration of GR into wider research and development activities. This would help to address inter-disciplinary questions that may arise in relation to the implementation of the various policies that are relevant to biodiversity, agriculture and forestry, including in the context of the European Green Deal in collaboration with research infrastructures such as LifeWatch and ELIXIR. It would also enable an easier uptake of the information by disseminating knowledge about GR to their end-users through dedicated portals such as the GenRes Gateway⁶⁹, the EU FarmBook⁷⁰, the Forest Information System for Europe⁷¹, the forest-based sector Technology Platform⁷² or a portal supporting the activities of the European coordination and information centre for conservation and sustainable use of agricultural GR that is proposed to be established in the European Strategy on GR developed in the frame of the GenRes Bridge project⁷³.

We propose here a set of overarching activities for the development of the data, numeric tools, resources and human skills that are necessary to assist both the common and the specific objectives of the three European networks ECPGR, ERFPP and EUFORGEN in terms of information and documentation⁷⁴. The aim of these activities is to support technically the development of a data resource on GR compliant with the FAIR principles (Figure 1) and the development of capacity for data stewardship and FAIR compliant data management at the key levels of the European networks, including the National Inventories.

A global consensus has emerged on the different steps of a data cycle in research activities to be addressed in a data management plan⁷⁵ and the distinct and necessary roles and skills of the persons involved in its design and implementation (Miksa *et al.* 2019; Figure 2). An important and still growing set of dedicated resources (guidelines, software, services, trainings, etc.) has been produced by a number of infrastructures, consortia and initiatives

⁶⁹ <https://www.genres.eu/>

⁷⁰ <https://h2020eureka.eu/about>

⁷¹ <https://forest.eea.europa.eu>

⁷² <https://www.forestplatform.org/>

⁷³ See section 3.1 of deliverable D2.4 – A European Genetic Resource Strategy

⁷⁴ See section 2.5 of deliverable D2.4 – A European Genetic Resource Strategy

⁷⁵ The different steps of the data life cycle and the associated good data management practices in the context of the life sciences are described for instance in the ELIXIR RDNkit (<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>)

(see section 1.2.2) and can be leveraged by the three networks in their overarching activities supporting documentation.

Figure 2 : Different areas of work of data stewards depending on their position in a research ecosystem according to Scholtens et al. 2019 : in the **Policy** area, they will define the policies of their institutions for specific data, use cases in the context of the FAIR guidelines and of legal obligations (e.g. GDPR); in the **Research** area, data stewards will adopt the appropriate workflows, tools, standards and infrastructures; in the **Infrastructure** area, they will facilitate the implementation of the FAIR guidelines through the development of softwares and hardwares, services and technical infrastructures. This illustrates the different points of views that are important to be addressed in data management: strategy and priorities, knowledge content and technicalities. This vision could be extended beyond academic research to private companies or extension services that can have their internal data policies and that might take into account possible collaborations with the academic sector.

2. Advance and coordinate the management of information associated with genetic resources conservation and sustainable use

The first set of recommendations will aim at driving all networks of stakeholders involved in GR documentation towards a coherent data management system, fitting to the FAIR guidelines, strengthening the central repositories and ultimately improving the services to GR users.

2.1. Develop and maintain the national inventories of plant, animal and forest genetic resources, which feed into the three European information management systems

The formalization of data management plans in the national inventories and at the scale of the whole networks would allow to revisit the flows of data (i) within countries to feed the national inventories and (ii) between the national inventories and the ECPGR, EUFORGEN and ERFP central information systems in relation not only with technical needs but also with the governance of the data from its collection to its curation. It would clarify the responsibilities of the stakeholders, identify technical and skill gaps and ultimately contribute to better address some causes of heterogeneity across countries. Finally, it would guide improvements in the interaction with partners contributing to GR characterization but not directly involved in the ECPGR, EUFORGEN and ERFP programmes. For instance, the archiving of data on GR that are no longer in the central repositories because they are no longer conserved or have been lost, might not be in the scope of a catalog of GR while it could still be important when characterization data exists or for retrospective analysis of trends. The perspectives of different stakeholders are important to decide what data should be archived and for what purpose.

Although the stakeholders and the flows of data are specific to each network, the different issues to be addressed in a data management plan are generic⁷⁶ and many tools have been developed to guide and support their development⁷⁷. A data management plan at the scale of the whole network will be a combination of several interlinked data management plans, including at least those of the national inventories and of the central repositories. Expertise and reusable training materials on data management⁷⁸ should be leveraged through a

⁷⁶ See for instance the guidelines developed by ELIXIR that encompass all types of data in the Life Sciences: [RDMkit \(elixir-europe.org\)](https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org)

⁷⁷ Some of these tools are listed in the RDMkit developed by ELIXIR : [Data management plan | RDMkit \(elixir-europe.org\)](https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org)

⁷⁸ Such trainings can be targeted to different audiences, e.g. data managers, managers of structures involved in data management or funding bodies. For instance, ELIXIR proposes links to trainings on tools that can be used to support specific steps of data management via crosslinks between its guidelines for data management (<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>) and its training portal (<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>), as well as webinars on the skills and roles of a data steward dedicated to managers of structures (e.g. [Towards professionalising data stewardship ; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769514](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769514)).

common action of the three programmes to (i) raise awareness about the subject at the national level, (ii) set up their strategies for the development of their respective data management plans (what different building blocks are used and what links connect them), and (iii) develop common (e.g. experience sharing) and specific activities aiming to support the development of the data management plans at the national level. These activities could also help in identifying and sharing experience on tools facilitating the collection and management of data in various types of partnerships (e.g. participatory activities, research projects, public private partnerships, ...).

2.2. Develop the three European information management systems to be compliant with the FAIR principles and to be recognized as trusted repositories

Based on the European Strategy on GR developed in GenRes Bridge and on current state of the art in terms of GR documentation in the three European networks for GR conservation, the need to improve the quality of services they provide in terms of documentation can be illustrated in relation to the main high level categories of activities, GR monitoring and GR use :

- **Improving the data quantity and quality for reporting on the conservation and management of GR.** At present, the documentation of *in situ* and on-farm conservation of GR across the three domains at the landscape level requires to integrate geographical data and georeferenced data held in EUFGIS, DAD-IS and for crops, Farmer's Pride⁷⁹ data sets. The documentation of *ex situ* conservation is managed by EURISCO for crops and the EUGENA portal for domestic animals⁸⁰; it is under development for forest trees. These lists of GR should all be associated with a status in terms of access and viability and all these data should be provided by the national inventories as complete as possible and regularly updated, which is still problematic. Moreover, the state of the art of conservation for a given genus of plant (e.g. cultivated species and wild relatives) whatever the conservation method (*ex situ*, *in situ* or on farm) requires to integrate data from different databases, not all included into the governance of the European networks of conservation of GR (e.g. EURISCO, EUFGIS, databases of botanical gardens, IUCN red list) on a common taxonomic backbone and taking into account different scales of units of conservation (individuals, populations). This is very far from being automatic, both because of the lack of common high level data models and data standards and technical implementation of the FAIR principles by the databases. Similar examples can be found in the animal domain (e.g. linking data from DAD-IS, ark farms, regional conservatories, local associations, and others).
- **Improving the data quantity and quality for research, breeding and forestry and farming activities.** Integrating the up-to-date GR catalogs described above with characterization data of these GR is important to foster the use of GR in adaptive strategies

⁷⁹ <http://www.farmerspride.eu/>

⁸⁰ [Home \(eugena-erfp.net\)](http://Home(eugena-erfp.net))

of agriculture and forestry. It requires automatic integration of data from the network's central catalogs with data held by other databases such as for instance international molecular data archives, databases holding phenotyping, soil or climatic data, bibliographic knowledge. The increasing use of DOI as identifiers for gene bank accessions will in the long run facilitate such data integration.

Tackling the issues described above and new ones emerging from the stakeholders of the three programmes of conservation of GR necessitate to align the infrastructures for documentation on GR and the data they hold with the FAIR principles to enable automatic data integration from different sources. It also necessitates active collaborations to reach consensus and ensure that common reference data (e.g. taxonomy), data standards, unique identifiers and guidelines are consistent across the different sources of data to be integrated and to enable the development of an e-infrastructure on GR in the spirit of the e-infrastructure for data on biodiversity as described by La Salle *et al.* 2016.

2.2.1. Developing a coherent set of guidelines for data standardization

The databases managing data on the conservation status of a given genus managed in different ways (e.g. in a conservatory orchard, *in situ*, on farm), might not use the same taxonomic reference, the access to reproductive material can vary and the accessions (i.e. an entry in a GR collection) can correspond either to single, well identified individuals or to populations. The coverage of certain types of data can vary, as shown for instance for geolocalisation data in the demonstration cases of GenRes Bridge¹⁰. Across the European information management systems, the key data for integration is the taxon and geolocalization and the re-use of data requires information on the type of accession (e.g. individual/population, domesticated/wild). The integration of data managed by the European information management systems with data managed in other databases to give access to knowledge about the characteristics (e.g. adaptation or production traits) depends on common standards for the key data that allow data integration (e.g. the GR accession and its type, traits description, localization). Enabling the automatic integration of data held by different databases requires agreement on common high level semantic data models, common standards and ontologies and, for some key data, common recommendations on data coverage.

It is therefore important to set up a coherent set of guidelines, reference data sets (e.g. reference taxonomy) and ontologies used for data on GR supporting the development of FAIR data by the Gene banks and their partners, the National Inventories and the European management information systems as well as their automatic integration with data maintained by other stakeholders.

Although some aspects related to data standardization are very specific for each of the European networks for GR conservation, many of them, important at high integration levels, are common (e.g. taxonomy, geolocation, genomic data). The strategies, processes and tools to facilitate the development of such standards and guidelines can also be similar even when the final product is different (e.g. how to link a GR accession with genomic data held in an international archive). A collaboration between the three European networks of GR conservation on these activities would foster the development of such resources and their adoption.

2.2.2. Implementing the FAIR principles in the three European information management systems

The central European Information management systems of ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN are the cornerstones of the e-infrastructure(s) needed by the three programmes. **They must align technically with the FAIR principles and be recognized as trusted, long term supported and well governed data repositories that enable uptake of their data by different types of portals dedicated to different types of users.**

They must develop a visible activity showing their continuous improvements in terms of aligning with the FAIR principles that ensure integration with other key resources but also other criteria that are important to ensure trust of the data users, transparency, responsibility, user focus, sustainability and technology (Figure 3 ; Lin *et al.* 2020).

This can be done through regular self-assessments such as those described in section 1.3.4. However, in the mid term, an official label of FAIRness and trustworthiness, should be considered together with an active strategy of registration in catalogs of repositories to enhance visibility. Some of these catalogs have recently implemented tools automatically checking for some high level FAIR and trust related criteria and make the results available to the public⁸¹, others allow to link repositories with standards and collections of resources

Figure 3. The TRUST principles to be met by digital repositories to ensure trustworthiness. They build on the Open Archival Information System reference model developed in 2012 by the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (<https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m2.pdf>) to which additional criteria ensuring trustworthiness were added. Adapted from Lin *et al.* 2020.

⁸¹ See for instance Re3data, a global registry of research data repositories funded by the German Research Foundation that covers research data from different academic disciplines : <https://www.re3data.org>

dedicated to specific communities⁸². These functionalities can be leveraged by the three programmes in different ways such as prioritizing important improvements to be done, up-to-date cataloguing of the resources promoted by the three programmes associated with citable references, outreach to the public and private research community. Again, sharing experience and practices between the persons in charge of the development of the three European information management systems would foster their respective activities as many issues are generic. It would also ensure coherent and synergic strategies in terms of visibility of the documentation systems in the global ecosystem of data repositories and would contribute to the missions of Forest Europe⁸³ and the proposed European coordination and information centre to support conservation and sustainable use of agricultural GR⁸⁴. Ultimately, the global visibility of the European information management systems of ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN as well as the data services they provide would increase.

3. Enabling transformative change

Managing GR as well as developing a FAIR data resource for GR are long term activities. The current organization and governance of the networks involved in the conservation of GR reflect the need for such a long-term endeavour: strong involvement of the countries' government bodies, mechanisms for decision making and for funding the network secretariats as well as for supporting their activities and common resources (e.g. their web sites and their central databases). Overarching coordination to improve cost-effectiveness, funding and impact of the activities of the three European networks, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN are proposed in the European Strategy on GR developed in the frame of the GenRes Bridge project⁸⁴. Regarding data management and the development of data services, this includes the development of a common web portal cataloguing the sources of information about GR⁸⁵ to be coordinated in the future for plant and domestic animal GR with the activities of the proposed European coordination and information centre for conservation and sustainable use of agricultural GR⁸⁴, or, for forest GR, of Forest Europe or of the Forest Information System for Europe⁸⁶. The GO FAIR initiative, in line with many other international initiatives or bodies, proposes other examples of activities that are necessary to change the culture of data management in the academic community, including raising awareness and developing measures acknowledging the efforts that are necessary for a high quality data management⁸⁷. Here we present overarching activities that could be developed to facilitate the shift toward a FAIR compliant culture of data management in the three European networks ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN.

⁸² FAIRsharing, a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata *standards*, inter-related to *databases* and data *policies* : <https://fairsharing.org/>

⁸³ <https://foresteurope.org/>

⁸⁴ See section 3.1 of deliverable D2.4 – A European Genetic Resource Strategy

⁸⁵ A first version of such a web information portal has been developed in the GenRes Bridge project, the GenRes Gateway (<https://www.genres.eu/>). The editors are the three secretariats of the European Programmes ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN and it provides users access to a catalog of databases on GR and technical guidelines, including about data standardization, but also other information (success stories, multimedia material, projects, etc.).

⁸⁶ Forest Europe : <https://foresteurope.org/>; Forest Information System for Europe: <https://forest.eea.europa.eu/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/go-fair-initiative/go-change/>

3.1. Raising awareness in the European networks, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN on FAIR data management and capacity building

It is important that the whole chain of persons involved in collecting, curating, storing and analysing data on GR for the national inventories and the European Information management systems are well aware of all aspects relevant to their role and trained accordingly. For this, it is necessary to dedicate trained stewards to pilot the documentation aspects of the conservation and sustainable use of GR in the national inventories and to organize this activity with a national mandate and a governance adequately supporting its mission, which necessitates also awareness of the governing and funding bodies in the countries. As mentioned in section 1.2, awareness on the importance of proper data management and on the FAIR principles as globally recognized guidelines has steadily grown over the last years not only in the academic community but also in government bodies. However, its translation into action is often lagging behind for each specific domain of activity. Developing data management plans as proposed in 2.1 should be associated with regular communication and discussions with the Secretariats of the European programs ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN but also with coordination bodies such as Forest Europe or the proposed European coordination and information centre to support conservation and sustainable use of agricultural GR⁸⁸ to ensure coordinated action supporting the improvements in terms of skills, governance and funding. The training resources developed in the frame of other initiatives should be leveraged to develop training programs for data officers, data stewards and data managers in charge of the documentation about GR⁸⁹.

The development of mechanisms for acknowledging the important efforts necessary for a TRUST and FAIR compliant data management is also an important generic activity that can benefit from coordination between ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN. It has been a constant preoccupation in the research community⁹⁰, involving the publishers and carrier- assessment bodies in the development of sets of reward and enforcement mechanisms. **The reward or enforcement mechanisms set up by the research community have to be leveraged by the three European networks, ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN but will have to be completed for the non academic stakeholders involved in documentation about GR.** The development of such new acknowledgement mechanisms should benefit from activities described in the section below.

⁸⁸ See section 3.1 of deliverable D2.4 – A European Genetic Resource Strategy

⁸⁹ Existing trainings can be promoted (e.g. RDA's training course can be advertised to research personnel involved in RG documentation - <https://rd-alliance.org/group/rdacodata-summer-schools-data-science-and-cloud-computing-developing-world-wg/outcomes-0>) as well as adapted to the specificities of data management on genetic resources and to new type of trainees.

⁹⁰ See for instance : Joachim Schöpfel, Otmane Azeroual. Rewarding Research Data Management. *Sci-K 2021: 1st International Workshop on Scientific Knowledge Representation, Discovery, and Assessment, Apr 19 – 23, 2021, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 2021, Ljubljana, Slovenia.* ([10.1145/1122445.1122456](https://doi.org/10.1145/1122445.1122456)). ([hal-03184357](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-03184357))

3.2. Develop a shared vision on legal and ethical issues associated with data sharing

A crucial point to enhance and diversify partnerships in GR collection, conservation and characterisation is related to data privacy, ownership and related ethical issues that will condition both the capacity to collect data and *in fine* its access. This issue is strongly linked to the building of trust between partners and is based on a good understanding of each other's expectations in terms of rewards from the partnership.

An illustrative example is the potential new barrier to data openness and reuse, which is emerging from the currently ongoing discussions regarding access to 'digital sequence information (DSI)' and associated benefit sharing (see section 1.2.2): the tension created by the advances in biotechnology and genome editing is here questioning data sharing in the field of genomics of GR. Another example relates to data from on-farm, and citizen based approaches for the conservation and characterization of GR: there are different types of participatory approaches in terms of (i) the degree of expertise that is delivered, from raw data to knowledge, (ii) expectations of the networks involved and (ii) associated legal and ethical aspects to be considered (e.g. Minet *et al.* 2017,⁹¹). The data policy must find a compromise between ethical, legal, confidentiality and technical issues: at the technical level, too many steps requiring authorizations for access make data integration nearly impossible, while authorization is one the levers of trust or might be mandatory according to the law⁹¹.

The development of good practices and shared views on data ownership and appropriate recognition for contributing partners would benefit from trans domain and multidisciplinary approaches⁹¹.

The development of a common shared vision on these aspects based on sharing expertise and knowledge in the field would also strengthen the capacity of the European networks for GR conservation to contribute to global debates in this ethical and legal area.

3.3. Increasing impact and sustainability

Managing data with high standards has a cost in terms of technical infrastructure, staff and skills (e.g. Juffe-Bignoli *et al.* 2016, OECD 2020). In relation to GR, it is a long term activity involving a complex network of contributors (gene bank managers, research partners, national focal points, central database managers, secretariats, etc.) that is globally underfunded, often through short term projects (Juffe-Bignoli *et al.* 2016). However, it has been estimated that the overall cost to the European economy of not having FAIR research data is €10.2 billion per year (OECD 2020). The benefits generated from access to data on GR can therefore be expected to outweigh the associated costs. Moreover the last report of IPBES underlines the importance of providing global knowledge on GR to develop adequate strategies for preventing further biodiversity loss worldwide⁹².

⁹¹ The multidisciplinary and multi stakeholders problem for ethically, legally and technically managing data about genetic resources or biodiversity has been pointed out by several recent projects: e.g. Wouter L, Alonso E, Bellisari L, *et al.* (2014). A roadmap of global research data infrastructures supporting biodiversity and ecosystem science. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2572.0083> and <https://www.dsmz.de/collection/nagoya-protocol/digital-sequence-information>

⁹² <https://ipbes.net/global-assessment>

The three European networks ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN are very successful in funding training and capacity building activities as recognized by their users⁹³. Mechanisms for funding data management activities have also been developed by the European Commission, including funding dedicated to infrastructures or to the development of the EOSC. Other funding bodies with a global scope, such as the Crop Trust⁹⁴, are also increasingly funding activities aimed at changing the data culture in the community of research in agriculture including the management of GR⁹⁵. Funding opportunity and fund raising is interlinked with expected and observed impact of the funded activity. Communicating the impact of activities related to FAIR compliant data management is an important objective of all initiatives aimed at supporting this activity and often takes the form of success stories⁹⁶ but can also be quantified in terms of improvement of quantity and quality of the data, increase in visibility and usage of the infrastructures, increase in collaborative projects etc.

Experience and knowledge sharing among the three European networks ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN aimed at improving funding the development and maintenance of their information management systems, including capacity building would help to identify new funding opportunities, to develop new funding mechanisms with relevant stakeholders and to improve their business models.

4. Entering the global coordination activities on data standardization and data documentation

GR are at the crossroads between different areas: biodiversity and environment, agriculture, forestry and life sciences. Many initiatives have been carried out during the last 10 years to facilitate the development of FAIR data resources in each of these areas. For instance, in the biodiversity area, the projects CReATIVE-B⁹⁷ and Biodiversity Knowledge⁹⁸ gathered various stakeholders, including from the GR area to scope what problems need to be addressed in order to develop a large resource of interoperable data on biodiversity. The Alliance for Biodiversity Knowledge proposed to organize a global consortium to progress in that direction⁹⁹. BiodivERsA¹⁰⁰, a European network of programmers and funders gathering 39 agencies and ministries from 25 European countries, has published in 2021 a typology and a mapping of the current research infrastructures dedicated to research on biodiversity,

⁹³ See GenRes Bridge deliverable D3.3. Report on current and potential new services for different user groups

⁹⁴ <https://www.croptrust.org>

⁹⁵ Two recent interesting examples in the crop domain are the development of a generic data management system for crop GR, GRIN Global, (<https://www.grin-global.org>) and the development of a standard for web services, the Breeding API, to enable machine actionable data sharing (www.brapi.org).

⁹⁶ For instance, the research data alliance has developed a collection in Zenodo and a set of adoption stories to give insights on its impact (<https://rd-alliance.org/about-rda/communication-kit>); GODAN, the Global Open Data for Agriculture and Nutrition, also communicate about its impacts stories (<https://www.godan.info/impact-stories>).

⁹⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/284441/reporting>

⁹⁸ <http://www.vliz.be/projects/biodiversityknowledge/>

⁹⁹ <https://www.biodiversityinformatics.org/en/#>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.biodiversa.org>

ecosystem services and nature-based solutions¹⁰¹. Finally, the EU commission has recently launched a Biodiversity Information system for Europe¹⁰².

In the Life Science area, ELIXIR has set up a Biodiversity focus group aimed at facilitating machine actionable integration of genomic data and other types of data held by infrastructures dedicated to the study of biodiversity and environment (GBIF, DiSSCo, Lifewatch, etc...; Waterhouse *et al. in press*)¹⁰³. The contributors to all these consortia are involved in networking activities of overarching global initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance or GODAN to develop common guidelines, recommendations and resources (see section 1.2.2). In return, the participating research institutes leverage the resources developed in these networking activities to better organize their data management and deliver FAIR data (e.g. Arnaud *et al.* 2020 ; Figure 4).

Figure 4. Use of the resources developed by the research community working on Agricultural data (focussed on crops) by the CGIAR to get their data compliant to the FAIR principles. From Arnaud *et al.* 2020.

It is crucial that the three networks develop specific and common activities to leverage the outputs of these international initiatives as much as possible, to address gaps related to GR (e.g. most of the initiatives cited above in the field of biodiversity are poorly addressing intra-specific diversity) and to contribute to global activities aiming at developing FAIR data resources.

Many common resources for data standardization and FAIR data management will have to be developed in the frame of global initiatives along with other important stakeholders such as USDA and CGIAR for the agriculture domain. The EU Commission has mechanisms for capacity building with neighbouring countries (pan Europe and Mediterranean basin) where centers of biodiversity are located. The three networks should gather their forces to bring

¹⁰¹ Manrique E., Blery C., Le Roux X., Mandon C. and all BiodivERsA partners. (2021). BiodivERsA Mapping of Biodiversity Research Infrastructures. BiodivERsA report, 108 pp. <https://www.biodiversa.org/1910/download>

¹⁰² <https://biodiversity.europa.eu/>

¹⁰³ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/biodiversity>

Europe as a continent and the mediterranean basin in international initiatives on GR FAIR data management to increase their impact on the conservation and use of GR. Such coordination will be increasingly necessary to support innovation in agriculture and forestry involving ecological principles or to monitor globally the diversity in the agro and forestry systems.

A coordinated pan-european voice will facilitate international cooperation on GR documentation.

5. Conclusion

The improvement of the data services provided to the diversity of stakeholders on GR conservation and use and the development of new ones, possibly not yet imagined, in relation with the current challenges faced by agriculture and forestry, require:

1. To advance and coordinate the management of information associated with GR conservation and sustainable use, including through networking activities described in section 2 of the present document and supporting the key commitments by 2030 2.5.1 and 2.5.2 proposed by the European Strategy on Genetic Resources:
 - KC 2.5.1. Develop and maintain the national inventories of plant, animal and forest GR, which feed into the three European information management systems, under a national mandate to deliver high quality documentation, with the support of the European GR programmes to improve capacity in FAIR compliant data management.
 - KC 2.5.2. Develop the three European information management systems to be compliant with the FAIR principles and to be recognized as trusted repositories, including through appropriate networking activities aimed at sharing good practices and expertise.
2. To identify important sources of data in Europe, network with, and change the culture of data of all stakeholders involved in the three European networks ECPGR, ERFP and EUFORGEN, improve the impact and sustain these activities for the long term through specific and synergic activities described in section 3 of the present document and supporting the key commitment by 2030 3.4.2 proposed by the European Strategy on Genetic Resources :
 - KC 3.4.2. Develop collaborative activities in support of information infrastructures to enable better findability, interoperability and access to all relevant sources of data and knowledge, develop a common ethic on data sharing, enhance outreach with global initiatives on linked open data, increase expertise in data stewardship among the different actors, and build capacity to address future documentation needs.
3. To actively network at the global level in the area of FAIR and linked data to ensure the visibility and contribution of Europe, at a pan-European level, to guidelines on data on GR, capacity building on FAIR data management and global knowledge on GR, through activities developed in section 4.

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Annex 1. Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of the documentation activities in the three networks

The expert partners of WP5 listed the strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of the documentation about genetic resources in the three European networks of GR conservation to support the development of the present deliverable.

AnGR	FGR	PGR
Strengths		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Domestic Animal Diversity Information System (DAD-IS) at global level and EFABIS at European level allows continuous assessment of risk status and trends of AnGR. - Through EUGENA, the countries support collaboration among gene banks to support <i>ex situ</i> conservation and to facilitate access to data and Gene bank collections -Breed societies and breeding organisations maintain private databases that include performance, pedigree and genomic data at breed level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Through EUFGIS the network of collaboration is wider than the EUFORGEN membership -EUFGIS, combined with climate data, allows continuous monitoring and reporting of the status of FGR conservation in Europe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECPGR has a strategy/roadmap for documentation in line with international commitments (GPA-PGR and IT-PGRFA) - European catalogue EURISCO as a central repository of <i>ex situ</i> PGR information relies on networking activity, providing capacity building, advice and harmonization across the European Gene bank information systems and a key service to the Global Information System. -Possibility of direct link of accessions in the EURISCO catalog to characterization data held in other global or regional archives -Well established accession-level standards for <i>ex situ</i> PGR passport data (MCPD)
Weaknesses		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Information about breeds and breed related gene bank collections in DAD-IS/EFABIS is not up to date, which hampers the accurate monitoring of status and trends of AnGR even though the data often exist at country level. -Limited interoperability of different databases (e.g. public-private, Gene bank-herdbook, and phenotypic-genomic). -Lack of records of performance , of genetic evaluation for endangered breeds and of geolocalized data. -The quality of some key data for linking knowledge and data from different communities is still difficult to curate in an efficient and sustainable way 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Not all countries in geographical Europe are part of EUFGIS -No molecular genetic knowledge data layer exists in EUFGIS. There is only a layer on environmental classification which is used as a proxy for the adaptive genetic variation in the information system and the pan-European strategy - very little characterisation data associated with conservation sites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Characterization is often made by distinct contributors outside the Gene bank community and thus poorly linked to EURISCO/GENESYS. The data is often scattered and not easily accessible and reusable. -The quality of some key data for linking knowledge and data from different communities (e.g. CWR or forest trees data with crops data) is still difficult to curate in an efficient and sustainable way (taxonomy, GPS location). -Lack of regional inventory of CWR at population level and of corresponding agreed documentation standards
Opportunities		

<p>-DAD-IS could facilitate monitoring conservation measures for endangered transboundary breeds. - Interoperability of different databases to explore the potential and value of breeds and farm animal genetic diversity -Database model implemented in the IMAGE portal in partnership with EMBL-EBI for animal genetic resources, www.image2020Genebank.eu</p>	<p>-It is possible to add new data layers (e.g. molecular, breeding value, administrative...) to EUFGIS and the pan-European strategy</p>	<p>-New technologies and resources not only facilitate the development of data services across several distinct and distant information systems, but also assist decision making, knowledge development and data curation by machine learning. -Broad recognition in all communities of the importance of Open science practices and FAIR guidelines -A willingness to apply these principles to operationally share and connect data in the Agrobiodiversity community to deliver services to users -The existence of resources (standards, ontologies, etc...) and communities of practice as starting blocks for building of guidelines -The existence of the CGIAR community to link with Mediterranean and Southern countries -The existence of central archives and tools, training and capacity building resources and governing mechanisms in the frame of ELIXIR and GBIF, with a growing collaboration between them.</p>
<p>Threats</p>		
<p>-Very limited public funding for development and maintenance of national and European databases for AnGR (<i>in situ</i> and <i>ex situ</i> data) -Gaps in documentation hamper efforts in conservation of AnGR - confidentiality issues for privately owned GR.</p>	<p>Limited public funding for development and maintenance of EUFGIS (and national information systems)</p>	<p>-Limitations on open access to digital sequence information might negatively affect the possibility to provide and use relevant information -Documentation (transversal to all domains): lack of dedicated long-term resources; lack of attractiveness for people involved in the domain with skills related to data science</p>

